

D8.1

Report on Project Management

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D8.1

Report on Project Management

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Abbreviations

- PC: Project Coordinator
- GA: General Assembly
- WPL: Work Package Leader
- EAB: Experts Advisory Board
- GA: Grant Agreement
- CA: Consortium Agreement
- EC: European Commission

Partners short names

TUB	(Technische Universität Berlin)
UNITELMA	(Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma)
UNI	(Ente Italiano di Normazione)
AUA	(Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon)
USC	(Universidad de Santiago de Compostela)
APRE	(Agenzia per la promozione della Ricerca Europea)
NOVA	(Nova - Institut für politische und Ökologische Innovation GMBH)
BAM	(Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und Prüfung)
RSB	(Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association)
ISEAL	(ISEAL Alliance)

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable sets out the basis for an effective management and coordination of the STAR4BBS project. It provides the overview of all management activities that will be put in place in order to assure the quality of all the results (e.g. deliverables) and the timely execution from all beneficiaries. Furthermore, it provides a point of reference on the work plan and quality assurance that will be applied throughout the project duration. This deliverable is linked to the implementation of T8.1, within the WP8 - Project Management & Internal Project Communication, and it is prepared by the project coordinator TUB

Disclaimer

The terms and provisions of the EU Grant Agreement (and its annexes) and the STAR4BBS Consortium Agreement will prevail in the event of any inconsistencies with recommendations and guidelines defined in the present report.

The author(s) of this deliverable have taken all available measures to ensure that the information contained in this Report is accurate, consistent, lawful, and up to date.

2 Introduction

This document is a collection of decisions, guidelines and instructions regarding the project management, administration and finances, as well as quality management of the STAR4BBS project. Its intention is to provide information regarding the procedures and pathways which will be followed during the project execution. The Report is based on terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement specifications and requirements.

The main objectives of the deliverable are:

- To provide all consortium partners with an overview of the management structure and their roles and responsibilities in the project, with defining the procedures for progress monitoring, quality assurance and risk and project management;
- To cover many of the day-to-day activities and standardize various procedures and elements of the project (e.g. project reports, deliverable submission etc.), ensuring a smooth implementation and in-time completion of the activities foreseen.

This deliverable is thus intended to be used by all project partners, to ensure quality assurance of project processes and outputs and prevent possible deviations from the project work plan as described in the Annex 1 - Description of Action of the Grant Agreement.

2.1 Purpose

The establishment of the Report on Project Management is part of the WP8 – Project Management & Internal Project Communication. The Report gives practical guide to project officer, management structure, and project partners for checking the progress of the project and assuring the quality of its outputs.

The document summarizes the key information, based on the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, the project management structures, the role and responsibilities of the different coordinating and management bodies, the decision-making procedures as well as the communication channels within the consortium. It outlines the reporting requirements for WP Leaders and other project partners, and the overall project monitoring and risk assessment procedures. Furthermore, it outlines the procedures to be followed by all project partners when preparing the project deliverables as well as when engaging in communication, publication and dissemination activities. Finally, the document outlines the rules for the document management.

3 Management structure

The project consortium consists of the decision bodies and leading roles within the STAR4BBS management team, as illustrated in Figure 1. They are implemented to support the overall project management and to ensure effective decision-making, clear and operational communication, and effective administrative control.

Figure 1 Management structure of STAR4BBS

The key roles in the STAR4BBS management structure are:

- Project Coordinator (PC)
- Work Package Leader (WPL)
- General Assembly
- Experts Advisory Board (EAB)

The consortium consists of in total 11 partners, of which six are beneficiaries, four* are associated partners, and one is an affiliated entity (Table 1).

Table 1 List of partners

Legal name of the entity	Short name	Country
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT BERLIN <i>Leader of WP4 and WP8 and project coordinator</i>	TUB	Germany
UNIVERSIDAD DE SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA <i>Leader of WP3</i>	USC	Spain
GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON <i>Leader of WP5</i>	AUA	Greece
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA <i>Leader of WP1</i>	UNITELMA	Italy
NOVA - INSTITUT FUR POLITISCHE UND OKOLOGISCHE INNOVATION GMBH <i>Leader of WP2</i>	NOVA	Germany
AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA <i>Leader of WP6, WP7</i>	APRE	Italy
ISEAL ALLIANCE	ISEAL	UK
RSB ROUNDTABLE ON SUSTAINABLE BIOMATERIALS ASSOCIATION	RSB	Switzerland
UNI - ENTE ITALIANO DI NORMAZIONE <i>Affiliated Entity</i>	UNI	Italy
STICHTING KONINKLIJK NEDERLANDS NORMALISATIE INSTITUUT* <i>(Better Biomass Certification System)</i>	NEN	Netherlands
BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG	BAM	Germany

* The participation status of the NEN as the STAR4BBS project partner is still pending. More explanation can be found in the *Critical implementation risks and mitigation measures* section of this report.

3.1 Project Coordinator

Project Coordinator (PC) plans overall technical, administrative and financial aspects of the project according to the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. The PC also monitors project execution and initiates corrective actions when needed. The PC is the main project representative and the formal communication point with the REA and other EC bodies. Coordinator regularly communicates with all project partner representatives, the Work Package and Task leaders, to monitor project outcomes' execution, informs the Consortium on the overall progress and makes suggestions for major changes or actions if necessary.

The STAR4BBS Project Coordinator is Luana Ladu from the Technical University of Berlin, as of M1 (from the beginning of the project). In addition, for the financial manager of the project, Juliane Rosengart will be responsible.

The PC is responsible for:

- Administrative and financial management
- Collection, review and submission of deliverables
- Quality and risk management
- External communication with partners, stakeholders and EC bodies
- Clustering activities with the other coordinators of sister projects financed under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZERO POLLUTION-07

APRE will support PC during the underlined activities regarding project management.

3.2 Work Package Leader

Work Package Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for the smooth and detailed monitoring, planning and execution of each Work Package and related Tasks. The main responsibilities include coordination of respective WP partners (Task Leaders, Project Partners); review and evaluation of the WP outcomes; cooperation with other WP leaders, to ensure the quality of the project's various phases; reporting to the Project Coordinator on the WP progress and any unexpected difficulties arising within a WP.

Figure 2 Schematic representation of WPs structure

The STAR4BBS WPLs are:

- WP1 - Review of international and EU SCS and labels: Enrica Imbert (UNITELMA)
- WP2 - Collection of data and figures on volumes: Olaf Porc (NOVA)
- WP3 - Identification of sustainability indicators and minimum requirements: Maria Teresa Moreira (USC)
- WP4 - Development of the monitoring system: Luana Ladu (TUB)
- WP5 - Assessment of costs of the adoption of SCS and labels and feasibility of B2B labels: Apostolis Koutinas (AUA)
- WP6 - Stakeholder involvement and development of recommendations: Serena Fabbrini (APRE)
- WP7 - Communication, dissemination and international cooperation: Serena Fabbrini (APRE)
- WP8 - Project management and internal project communication: Luana Ladu (TUB)

3.3 General Assembly

The General Assembly is the decision-making body of the consortium. As indicated in the Consortium Agreement, The General Assembly consists of one representative of each Party (beneficiary) and one representative of ISEAL. Each Member is duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 6.3.7 of the Consortium Agreement.

The Project Coordinator chairs all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise by the General Assembly. The Parties agree to abide by all decisions of the General Assembly.

The General Assembly is the ultimate decision-making body of the STAR4BBS consortium as well as a problem-solving entity. Therefore, it will cover potential issues of intellectual property rights and address problem-solving strategies to deal with internal disputes, if necessary. The procedures for decision-making are described in detail in the CA.

3.4 Experts Advisory Board

The Experts Advisory Board (EAB) is a consultation body that advises the Consortium, by providing valuable external and impartial recommendations and opinions on the project topics' issues and outcomes, in order to maximize the STAR4BBS exploitation potential.

The members of the EAB will be invited to join relevant stakeholder engagement activities (such as co-creation workshops), related to specific activities and tasks of the project or individually contacted to provide advice and feedback based on their knowledge and expertise. The EAB members can also be invited to join General Assembly meetings to support and facilitate the decisions made but shall not have any voting rights.

STAR4BBS is a Coordination and Support action, which addressed the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07: International and EU sustainability certification schemes for bio-based systems. Two other projects – HARMONITOR (led by Sergio Ugarte - SQ Consult) and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (led by Iris Vural Gursel – Stichting Wageningen Research) were also awarded to address the same call. Together with the project officers of the REA, the three projects decided to form one Joint Expert Advisory Board, instead of a separate board for each project. This clustering activity will facilitate receiving feedback from experts from other organizations that are part of other two projects' consortium.

As described in detailed in the D7.2 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, upon discussion between the 3 coordinators, a joint list of experts was compiled, and a division was made between the coordinators to contact each expert. These experts were accordingly contacted by the coordinators and already confirmed their participation. Additional experts may become part of the Joint EAB during further implementation of the project.

The members of the Joint EAB are external experts and are independent from the projects and their consortia. They are selected on the basis of being recognized experts, having a certain expertise relevant for the cluster projects. They cover together a range of expertise and represent range of stakeholder categories including: industrial bio-based value chain actors, sustainability system community, academia, and international organizations. Their participation is voluntary and unremunerated. Members will be invited by the coordinators on behalf of the three consortia.

The joint advisory board is so far composed of 8 external experts selected based on their experience and expertise. The members' list is included in the Table 2.

Table 2 List of the experts from the selected Joint EAB

Name	Affiliation	Expertise
Ms. Constance Ißbrücker	European Bioplastics	Deputy Managing Director / Head of Environmental Affairs, among others responsible for Sustainability of bioplastics and Standardisation and certification of bioplastics
Mr. Mario Bonaccorso	SPRING - Italian Circular Bioeconomy Cluster	Cluster Manager at SPRING, development of biobased industries in Italy in a sustainable way with a focus on regional territorial players
Dr. Audrun Utskarpen	Ecolabelling Norway	Senior Environmental Advisor, among others knowledge on ecolabels and their role in reducing the environmental impact of products
Mr. Santiago Fernandez De Cordoba	United Nations Forum on Sustainability Standards (UNFSS)	Coordinator of the UNFSS, head UNCTAD Sustainability Standards Program analysing potential effectiveness and development impact of sustainability schemes from the perspectives of developing-countries
Mr. Marco Rupp	Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC)	Public Affairs & Sustainability Manager
Ms. Jenny Walthher-Thoss	Berndt+Partner Consultants	Senior Consultant Sustainability, expertise in sustainability standards and certification, sustainable biomass and supply chains
Dr. Martin Greimel	University of Natural Resources and Life Science Vienna	Head of the Center for Bioeconomy, coordination of all bioeconomy related research
Ms. Susanna Albertini	FVA New Media Research	Managing Director, co-creation and creativity enabling factors, communication, impact and valorisation of research results with experience on sustainable circular bioeconomy

In addition to the above listed eight experts that already confirmed their participation, there is pending confirmation from two other organizations whose contribution was identified as of value for the three projects: Textile Exchange, and the European Chemical Industry Council (CEFIC). In addition, the coordinator of the STAR4BBS project has had two meetings with the FAO in order to explore the possibility of including this organization in the Joint EAB. Negotiations are ongoing.

If during the project implementation, further expertise is identified as missing in the Joint EAB, additional members will be nominated on an ad-hoc basis.

The composition and the members of the Joint Experts Advisory Board will be publicly acknowledged on the project websites, unless a Joint EAB member explicitly asks for her/his membership to remain confidential. The membership lasts for entire duration of the projects (36 months). The membership is terminated automatically with the end of the three projects (SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS). The members may request their membership to be terminated at any time in writing by email. The members provide their input and advice on a voluntary basis. There is no contractual obligation to the consortium, but commitment to cooperate, actively participate and provide advice.

3.4.1 Terms of references of the Joint EAB

The main purpose of the Joint Experts Advisory Board is to provide advice and guidance to the implementation of relevant activities and tasks of the projects. Being a member of the Advisory Board will entail participation in the Advisory Board Meetings (target: twice a year), gathering early knowledge of the results of the three projects, and having the opportunity to provide feedback, criticism

Specific tasks include:

- Monitor and critically review the projects' development and progress in meeting their stated objectives;
- Providing input and feedback to the projects based on their knowledge and expertise, in among others, the following topics:
 - Selection of sustainability certification schemes and labels for bio-based systems;
 - Purpose and concept of a monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness of existing certification schemes and labels;
 - List of sustainability policy targets;
 - Selection of indicators to be included in the monitoring system;
 - Monitoring system structure and layout;
 - Application of the monitoring system to selected certification schemes and labels;
- Advise about long-term and short-term strategic decisions of the projects;
- Help the consortia to stay up to date with the developments related to the project, whether in standards, schemes/ecolabels, legislation, industry or research on sustainability and bioeconomy;
- Facilitate connection with the targeted stakeholder groups to join the organized stakeholder engagement activities;

- Bring alignment with ongoing international efforts (especially for international organizations);
- Contribute to the wider dissemination of project results with relevant stakeholders via their network and thereby support sustainability of project outcomes beyond the project lifetime.

The responsibilities of the Joint EAB include:

- Participation in the Joint EAB meetings;
- Participation in stakeholder engagement activities organized by the cluster projects (e.g., workshops, meetings and other events) throughout the project to provide feedback on the research findings, to bring input relevant for the research conducted, and bring recent developments to consortia knowledge.

3.4.2 Rules of procedure of the Joint Experts Advisory Board

Meetings with the Joint AB are intended to be organized at least once a year. During these meetings, the three sister projects will present progress, show preliminary research findings and ask for input and feedback from the Joint EAB. After each meeting minutes will be prepared including recommendations of the Joint EAB to be adequately taken into consideration in the execution of the project. The meeting minutes will be circulated to the joint Joint EAB for comments and approval.

In addition, the members of the Joint EAB will be invited to join the stakeholder engagement activities related to their expertise organized by the cluster projects (e.g., co-workshops, meetings and other events) throughout the project (3 years). The members of the Joint EAB can participate in General Assembly meetings of each project upon invitation. They shall have an advisory role in these meetings and shall not have any voting rights. All these meetings are envisaged to be mostly in the form of online meetings. The STAR4BBS project plans to invite the Joint EAB in at least one of the three physical plenary consortium meetings (described in the Meetings section of this report). The Joint EAB will be notified about any upcoming meetings and events in advance (~ 3 weeks). A draft agenda shall be shared in advance. In addition, they could be invited to the online quarterly project meetings (to assist and facilitate the decisions made, advise on long-term strategy making etc.).

Direct contacts (e-mail or video call) with individual members may also occasionally be arranged to seek specific input, advice and feedback based on their knowledge and expertise. The partners have the ultimate legal responsibility for the conduct of the project as the beneficiaries are bound by the Grant Agreement. The Joint EAB will make recommendations to the consortium, which will in turn take actions as necessary with regards to these recommendations. The Joint EAB recommendations however are not binding for the consortium that may accept, amend or reject them.

In case of physical participation in plenary consortium meetings, the travel and accommodation expenses of the Joint EAB members will be covered in line with the project budget rules (e.g., economy class). Reimbursement will be made based on original receipts and justifications.

3.4.3 Confidentiality

The Joint EAB has the duty to protect all confidential and non-public information, such as draft versions of the project deliverables, preliminary findings or contents of the discussions within the Joint EAB meetings. The projects' coordinators will ensure that a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) or a confidentiality declaration is executed between all partners and each Joint EAB member. As per the Consortium Agreement of the STAR4BBS, the Coordinator is to sign on behalf of all partners, an NDA with each member of the EAB, in order to protect Confidential Information disclosed by any of the partner to any member of the EAB. With the decision of a Joint EAB, it is considered that the projects will jointly prepare a confidentiality agreement to be signed by each of the Joint EAB member.

A member of the EAB shall not participate in any discussion where a situation or circumstance of a personal or professional nature can compromise his/her ability to provide advice and recommendations in the interest of best performing his/her objectives and tasks.

4 Administrative Management and Project Coordination

4.1 Day-to-day management

Daily project management activities are performed by the project coordinator with the support of APRE, in particular administration, control of work progress and quality management.

In the light of ensuring the effective coordination, implementation and management of STAR4BBS activities, a detailed Excel database in form of a Project Checklist has been prepared, based on the STAR4BBS Gantt table. WPLs and Task leaders are encouraged and reminded by the project coordinator on a regular basis, to use the database to ensure smooth and operational workflow.

The PC together with WPLs assigns tasks and oversees task division and provides daily assistance in activities implementation, in accordance with the Consortium Agreement (CA). The Coordinator organized the signing of the Consortium and Grant Agreement (GA) among the Consortium.

As one of the outcomes of the project's kick-off meeting (see more in the Annex 1.1, and 1.2), it was agreed that a Project Glossary is produced, for aligning all the terms and definitions to be used throughout the project. The Glossary was made and is daily maintained by the PC, who also shared it with all project partners. Consortium was invited to use this document accordingly and to give their input, as it is not a closed document, but open to changes and constantly updated.

4.2 Financial management

4.2.1 Internal financial management

TUB as project coordinator has an extra department for the administrative and financial processing of EU projects. During the Kick-off meeting of the STAR4BBS project in Berlin, the STAR4BBS financial officer, Ms. Rosengart Juliane, provided a presentation on the financial management of the project. In particular, different administration rules and financial management aspects were addressed.

In the financial department, the money from the EU is accepted and allocated to the project account. The project account is generated in SAP and consists of a 12-digit number sequence, which is used only for the financial processing of this project. When the project is created in the SAP system, all project relevant data are entered, such as project manager, duration, budget and allowed output types. Once the project has been created, an authorized person (key user) must check the entries and release the project for processing. Once the project has been released in SAP, authorized employees can access it. For each project, a digital file is created and can be accessed by all employees of Department V Research. In the STAR4BBS file all data related to this project are stored, including: the Grant Agreement (GA), the Consortium

Agreement (CA); the information about the overall budget; Information about partner budget, settings, settlements, projections as well as correspondence.

The calculations of partner payments and their instructions are double-checked by a colleague and only then forwarded to the finance department for posting. Financial data can also be accessed and maintained only by authorized persons, i.e. with employment one is assigned the level of authorization. This depends on the position in which one is employed at the Technical University. Only authorized employees with two-factor authentication can log into the corresponding financial portals. All transactions are given their own voucher number in the finance department when they are posted, under which this posting can be traced and retrieved. All vouchers are kept in our internal archive for 10 years.

The financial department always informs the project managers about regulations and innovations that must be complied with, for example in procurement - a comparison of offers has to be made. Depending on the amount of the award, our internal procurement department is involved to comply with all guidelines and to provide evidence of complete documentation in the event of an audit. The financial department advises as well on what may be purchased over the project budget and what must be financed from overhead.

Already when applying for a project we work closely with the project leaders and calculate the budget, calculate the personnel costs and person months - reconcile these figures. If we are the coordinator, we check the interim reports for plausibility.

Are the personnel costs within the requested limits. Are actual costs accounted for in the personnel costs and no lump sums. What about the other costs or travel costs - are they within the limits or is there already an overspend to be seen. Internally, we always make projections in order to identify and compensate for any misapplications in the budget. We take the data for the projections from our own internal reporting tool. Here, too, the use for employees is role-specific - not everyone is allowed to see everything and generate reports. Therefore, this tool can only be accessed and used via two-factor authentication. All processes and work steps are carried out in close cooperation with the project manager or the scientific staff assigned to the project.

4.2.2 Payments to project partners

TUB received the pre-financial of the project at the end of August 2022. TUB has allocated the budget (75% pre-financing) to the difernet beneficiaries, at the beginning of September, 2022. A 5% was kept by the EU as the Guarantee Fund.

The financial officers of each beneficiary partner, are informed to use the Templates for financial reporting, included in the Funding & Tender portal.

The TUB financial manager is planning to organize a webinar with all the partners financial managers in June 2023 in order to provide guidance for preparing the first interim report. If needed, they can contact any time the TUB financial manger via email and arrange bilateral online meetings.

4.3 Document management

The procedures and processes are in place to ensure consistency, confidentiality, security and traceability in terms of document management.

All project partners have agreed that a Project Document Repository is used for internal communication, collaboration and exchange of drafts, intermediate data and final version files, throughout the duration of the project (three years). This type of project platform will: ease the access of the whole Consortium to files and folders which are to be shared for project-related purposes; enable PC and WPLs to oversee work progress; facilitate document distribution, review and other processes.

Initially, the Google Drive was used as a repository platform, but due to several technical issues experienced by a few project partners in its use and due to the policies adopted by the European Commission regarding the use of online tools which have their servers located in Europe, a new platform had to be initiated (from M3). Thus, **tubCloud** (<https://tubcloud.tu-berlin.de/>) has been set up as a new repository, configured by the TUB (Coordinator) and led and maintained by the TUB and APRE.

Each WPL is responsible for the maintenance of their own respective WP folder, and they incentivize respective Task leaders and all other partners for using, sharing and uploading repository documents. All important project management documents can also be found on the cloud.

Name	Size	Modified
1. Grant Agreement	3.5 MB	7 days ago
2. Deliverables	0 KB	7 days ago
3. EU Documents & Reports	42.5 MB	7 days ago
WP1 - Review of SCS and labels for feedstock, bio-based materials and products	12.7 MB	2 days ago
WP2 - Collection of data and figures on volumes of biological feedstock and bio-based	12.8 MB	7 days ago
WP3 - Identification of sustainability indicators and minimum requirements	0 KB	7 days ago
WP4 - Development and demonstration of a monitoring system	28.2 MB	18 hours ago
WP5 - Assessment of costs of the adoption of SCS & labels and feasibility	0 KB	7 days ago
WP6 - Stakeholder involvement, and development of recommendations	1.2 MB	4 days ago
WP7 - Communication, dissemination and international cooperation	152.8 MB	19 hours ago
WP8 - Project Management _ Internal Project Communication	161.6 MB	20 hours ago

Figure 3 STAR4BBS repository structure

The service of the cloud is hosted on the Technical University of Berlin servers, secured from unauthorized access. Local copies of the files and folders are also kept as a backup. The OnlyOffice program is used for editing and sharing files.

TUB provided instructions on how to use the new repository and incentivized partners (especially WPLs) to use it on a daily basis, in particular for imminent need of receiving feedback and comments on certain results.

4.3.1 Deliverables

A total of 35 deliverables needs to be submitted to the European Commission over the project implementation (Table 3). Project Coordinator will ensure efficient, timely and high-quality delivery of all deliverables.

The status of upcoming and pending deliverables will be monitored by the WP leaders and reported to the Project Coordinator. Any obstacles or expected delays should be flagged immediately providing an explanation, with planned mitigation action and the anticipated completion date.

There are different levels of dissemination for the deliverables. They can either be Public (fully open) or Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement).

A deliverable template, specifically designed by project communication team (APRE) can be found on the tubCloud (under STAR4BBS Repository > WP7 – Communication, dissemination and internal cooperation > 7.2. – Dissemination and communication tools and activities > Template > Deliverable Template) and will be used as the basis for every deliverable.

Tracking completion of the project’s achievements is enhanced with identification of 8 **milestones**, which serve as project checkpoints and represent the finalization of a project phase, aiding the evaluation and monitoring of project progress. The list of STAR4BBS milestones can be found in Table 4.

Table 3 Overview of the STAR4BBS deliverables

Acronym	Title	Responsible partner	Due month	Dissemination level
D1.1	Report on policy sustainability targets	NOVA	M6	SEN - Sensitive
D1.2	Report on existing international and EU SCS and B2B labels for feedstock and bio-based materials & products	UNITELMA	M12	PU - Public
D1.3	Report on impact and contribution of existing SCS and B2B labels	ISEAL	M12	PU - Public
D1.4	Report on existing monitoring schemes, with recommendations for new system	TUB	M12	PU - Public
D2.1	Concept and methodology for collecting volumes of biogenic feedstock	NOVA	M12	PU - Public
D2.2	Report on matching biogenic flows with certification systems	NOVA	M18	PU - Public
D2.3	Report on selected test cases	AUA	M18	SEN - Sensitive

D2.4	Report on volumes of biogenic feedstocks and bio-based products and material	NOVA	M24	SEN Sensitive	-
D2.5	Impact assessment of SCS on market access and trade	NOVA	M24	SEN Sensitive	-
D3.1	Report on sustainability indicators for the monitoring system based on Life Cycle assessment	USC	M12	PU - Public	
D3.2	Report on additional indicators of monitoring system	USC	M15	PU - Public	
D3.3	Report on metrics, thresholds and minimum requirements for sustainability indicators	AUA	M24	PU - Public	
D3.4	Sustainability requirements for the monitoring system	USC	M34	PU - Public	
D4.1	Concept of the monitoring system	ISEAL	M12	PU - Public	
D4.2	Monitoring system tool	TUB	M30	PU - Public	
D4.3	Report on the testing and ranking	TUB	M36	SEN Sensitive	-
D5.1	Report on assessment of externalized environmental and social benefits and costs	AUA	M30	SEN Sensitive	-
D5.2	Report on assessment of techno-economic costs and benefits and integrated life cycle costing	AUA	M32	SEN Sensitive	-
D5.3	Report on feasibility best of awarded B2B labels	UNITELMA	M36	SEN Sensitive	-
D6.1	STAR4BBS stakeholder map	APRE	M5	PU - Public	
D6.2	Report on key feedback from STAR4BBS co-creation workshops	APRE	M24	SEN Sensitive	-
D6.3	STAR4BBS Recommendations for increasing the uptake and harmonization of SCS and labels	NOVA	M36	PU - Public	
D7.1	Strategy for dissemination, exploitation and Communication	APRE	M6	PU - Public	
D7.2	Report on Dissemination, Communication and networking activities	APRE	M34	PU - Public	
D7.3	Action Plan for joint activities with other projects funded under the ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 topic	TUB	M6	PU - Public	
D7.4	Mid-term clustering report for HORIZONCL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07	TUB	M18	PU - Public	
D7.5	First Policy Brief	APRE	M18	PU - Public	
D7.6	STAR4BBS final conference Report	APRE	M36	PU - Public	

D7.7	Final clustering report for HORIZONCL6-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 2021-	APRE	M36	PU - Public
D7.8	Roadmap for STAR4BBS' outputs exploitation	UNITELMA	M34	PU - Public
D7.9	Final Policy Brief	TUB	M36	PU - Public
D8.1	Report on project management	TUB	M4	PU - Public
D8.2	Initial Data Management Plan	UNITELMA	M6	PU - Public
D8.3	Ethical issues report	TUB	M4	PU - Public
D8.4	Final Data Management Plan	UNITELMA	M36	PU - Public

Table 4 Milestones in STAR4BBS project

No	Name	Responsible partner	Work Package No	Due month
1	STAR-ProBio database updated	UNITELMA	WP7	M6
2	Review of existing international and EU SCS and B2B labels completed	UNITELMA	WP1	M12
3	Test cases selected	AUA	WP2	M18
4	Final selection of metrics and thresholds for the indicators	USC	WP3	M34
5	Monitoring system developed	TUB	WP4	M30
6	Report on process design of test cases, value chains and alternative recirculation EoL scenarios	AUA	WP5	M24
7	List of recommendations to be circulated within different stakeholders	NOVA	WP6	M34
8	Onsite final conference	APRE	WP7	M36

4.3.2 Meeting minutes and agendas

Each WPL is responsible for managing meetings under their respective work package, including preparing and sharing meeting minutes, and asking for partners' feedback and approval. They should also prepare the agenda and share it in advance (with the link in case of an online meeting) with respective partners. PC will be available for giving an initial input if needed, as well as for review and proposing adjustments, if deemed necessary, to the mentioned documents.

4.4 Meetings

Within the framework of the STAR4BBS project there are two types of meetings – internal, within the Consortium members, and external, towards all other audiences. These meetings are envisioned mostly as online (virtual) calls, and in some instances as in-person (live) meetings.

4.4.1 Internal (Consortium) meetings

Internal meetings are organized either on a regular basis (e.g. Quarterly Project Meetings) or as periodic and ad-hoc calls, when necessary (e.g. WP calls).

These meetings can be classified as:

- Internal Kick-off meetings

Two such meetings were organized by the PC. The goal was to build a work team for an effective and smooth project implementation. The first one was held at the very beginning of the project, on September 1st, 2022 in an online setting (see Annex 1.1). The second one was organized between 14th and 15th September 2022 (see Annex 1.2). It was a hybrid event, with majority of partner representatives coming in person and several project partners also connecting online (all confirmed project partners and associated partners participated in the meeting).

- Quarterly Meetings with Agenda including topics, participants list, results of the meeting and to-do list integrated into minutes

The first quarterly project meeting is planned as an online event on the 13th of December 2022, from 10 to 13h.

- WPLs monthly meetings
- Onsite meetings planned for M12, M24 and M36, and online meetings (M6, M18, M30)
- Additional ad-hoc online meetings

4.4.2 External meeting

Next to the above-described meetings and calls among Consortium partners, other types of meetings will be held with the members of the Advisory Board, sister project partners, EC representatives and other stakeholders.

- Joint kick-off meeting with sister projects (June 2022) (T7.3)

As a STAR4BBS project coordinator, TUB participated in June this year in the joint kick-off external meeting of the EC representatives and partners of the three projects financed under call topic HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZERO POLLUTION-07, and presented an overview of the project and the related tasks and activities. The three projects agreed on future cooperation, mutual approach to finding synergies between them and working in cohesion.

- Inter-projects meetings – periodical and ad-hoc

TUB is responsible for the liaison with HARMONITOR and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The three project coordinators agreed to meet every 6 weeks. However, ad-hoc additional meeting will be organized when needed. To date, five external meetings with project coordinators have already been organized.

The three sister projects created 8 different inter project teams (Annex II). Each group have already met at least once in the course of the past four months.

5 Communication

5.1 Internal communication

The consortium's internal communication strategy is aimed at ensuring effective and collaborative interaction among the project partners, but also on timely delivery, collection and storage of information. Project coordinator will liaise internal communication in order to make it as swift and precise as possible, with assistance from APRE. Methods and channels of communication will include email, web meetings (Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Google Meets, Skype) and face-to-face meetings, and document sharing (as noted before).

5.1.1 Email

Day-to-day communication will be based mostly on **e-mail** exchange, so that the frequent communication within the consortium is maintained. To facilitate rapid e-mailing and ensure the correct inclusion of involved persons, the project **mailing list** has been created by APRE (Excel file available on tubCloud) and uploaded and shared with all partners via cloud.

It is the responsibility of each project partner to actively and timely inform the Project Coordinator and Communication leader on changes of contact details or additional persons involved. The mailing list will be reviewed and updated regularly. Additional lists can be set up upon request if necessary (e.g. at WP level).

E-mails with file attachments should be avoided with the preference given to sharing links and file locations on the tubCloud. This is important for reducing the risk of exceeding the email quota and for tracking the latest file version when receiving input from several partners at the same time. Important messages about the upcoming meetings, impending deliverables and other issues with high priority, should contain specific description and highlighted deadline, if applicable.

5.2 External communication

Communication to the external audience is managed within the WP7 - Communication, dissemination and international cooperation, and partly within the WP8 - Project management and internal project communication.

As leader of WP7, APRE will be responsible for the visibility and outreach of the project through promotion and communication, with the assistance of PC and the whole consortium: more detail of the Communication strategy will be appointed in D7.1 Strategy for dissemination, exploitation and communication (due to M6).

As a part of both external communication and stakeholder engagement (WP6 and WP7), APRE had created Database Subscription Form (see in Annex of the D8.3), for stakeholders which wish to receive news, newsletters and information on events organized by STAR4BBS consortium.

5.2.1 Communication with sister projects partners

Two other projects (HARMONITOR and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED) have been selected by the EC for funding under the same call topic HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZERO POLLUTION-07. In June 2022, there was a joint kick-off meeting of these three projects and REA representative, in order to target synergies between them and align the work on maximizing the potential of sustainability certification schemes and labels to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy. For this reason, a regular communication has been established among the WP and Task leaders of all three projects, as well as project coordinators. Periodic online meetings and extensive email exchange are being conducted, with the purpose of activities and outcomes' alignment and avoidance of duplication of the work. The meetings organized in the first months of the start of the STAR4BBS project with other two sister projects partners are described earlier in the report, under Meetings.

5.2.2 Communication with the project officer of the EC

The PC is solely responsible for the communication with the Project Officer (PO) of the EC, respective to the project. Besides regular communication via email exchange and attendance of joint meetings with sister projects partners, through mutual agreement it was decided that PC will deliver regular short **progress reports** to PO every 3 months. The first activity report was sent to Stefania Rocca (REA) on 27th October 2022 and finalized and submitted after two rounds of revision. Future project reporting will be kept up to date and in a timely fashion.

In addition, the PC has the responsibility of submitting **all project-related reports and deliverables** to the EC, with providing additional information and further clarification if requested. Also, the PC will keep all partners informed and updated about any important communication with the EC.

6 Quality management

The STAR4BBS Consortium will have a result-oriented and perspective approach throughout the project duration with a special attention towards quality assurance. The quality of project activities and outputs will be monitored by WP and Task leaders and the Project Coordinator according to the roles and responsibilities defined in section (§2) Management Structure – Roles and Responsibilities and in the project related documents: Grant Agreement and its Annexes, and in the Consortium Agreement specifications and requirements.

Monitoring of the project's progress and activities and deciding on any actions necessary to correct potential deviations from the plan is the responsibility of the PC.

Quality assurance and control measures will ensure that the project remains consistent during its lifetime and that the results of STAR4BBS are of a continuous high level of quality.

6.1 Control of work progress

Specific activities were divided and delegated among project team members, by the project coordinator. Specifically, responsibilities for individual tasks (of high priority) within the WP1, WP2 and WP4 were established. Along the line of project management (WP8) activities, evaluation and validation of tasks were decentralized to the level of work package leaders (of WP1, WP4 and WP7). WPLs will further redistribute the tasks to the relevant Task leaders. This will ensure timely delivery of project results (deliverables, milestones, reports, events, etc.).

All partners will be contacted and asked for their inputs, comments and suggestions when decision-making process is in question, using an all-inclusive and consensus-based management style.

PC is responsible for steering project activities and outcomes and for monitoring project implementation and results achieved.

Quality control measures will include KPIs and quality assurance of deliverables (at critical stages: review, proofreading, submission etc). Project Checklist will be used as a management tool to keep on track all project activities and outcomes, throughout the duration of the project.

The authors of all deliverables at the review stage will allow minimum 7 days for the other project partners to share their input and feedback, and make sure to send the final version of the deliverable to PC at least one week before the due date.

6.2 Risk assessment and mitigation

The Project Coordinator will be mainly responsible for handling internal and external risks and informing all partners when necessary. In proposal phase, the Consortium has identified the possible risks and critical issues that could negatively affect the overall

quality or jeopardize the successful results of the STAR4BBS project (Critical risks & risk management strategy).

As project coordinator, TUB is responsible for coordinating the risks management actions within the consortium, while WP leaders are responsible for risk management within their respective WP.

6.3 Conflict management

STAR4BBS Consortium adopts a proactive approach to decision making and dispute settlement based on dialogue and deliberation. All partners have agreed within the Consortium Agreement to attempt solving amicably their conflicts, either on technical, financial or procedural issues.

If possible, disputes should be dealt at the lowest decision-making body level. If necessary, a meeting will be held with all representatives of the respective level. In case of failure, a meeting at upper level will be arranged. For all conflicts/disagreements, standard voting procedures will be followed according to the provision of the Consortium Agreement (Section 6.3.3 Voting rules and quorum).

6.4 Reporting

Partners must keep track of all their publications and dissemination activities related to the STAR4BBS Project. These publications and activities will be reported to the Project Coordinator through the shared drive. APRE, as leader of WP7 – Communication, dissemination and international cooperation, will maintain the overall list of publications and dissemination activities and ensure that this list is well reflected on the designated page on the STAR4BBS website.

6.5 Critical implementation risks and mitigation measures

The PC will continuously monitor and assess risks identified in the Grant Agreement under the List of critical risks. Verification of critical risks for implementation and mitigation measures will be included in the Data Management Plan and subjected to work plan refinement and update. Project partner UNITELMA already started working on the elaboration of the Data Management Plan.

Ethical issues are covered in the deliverable D8.3, which provides a general overview of all ethical issues associated with the implementation of STAR4BBS project. It describes how ethical issues and data protection requirements are addressed in the different activities, to comply with the highest standards of research ethics and integrity, and with the EU, national and international law. In particular, the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, and the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon EUROPE /2020 (Horizon Europe regulation 2021/695) are rigorously applied. All participant institutions are required to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and EU Directive 95/46/EC on Data Protection.

The potential minor risk after the start of the project implementation occurred with NEN representative leaving his position at the organization (Jarno Dakhorst was

involved in preparation of the project proposal). Therefore, the way in which NEN will participate in the project as associated partner is not yet fully defined. In principle, NEN was invited to join the consortium as an Associate partner because of the Better Biomass Certification System (own and managed by NEN). The idea is that the Better Biomass Certification will provide inputs to the project and will be tested with the STAR4BBS monitoring system. Currently, NEN has reduced its activities in the implementation and management of Horizon Europe projects related to the bio-based economy. This is especially the case, because of the reduced standardization activities under CEN/TC411 (led by NEN). However, the PC has discussed with a consultant on energy standardization at NEN (Emiel Janssen) and with the person currently managing the Better Biomass Scheme (Harmen Willemse), the possibility of having a direct participation of the scheme in the project activities. This proposal is currently being internally discussed within NEN. Harmen Willemse will attend the project meeting on the 13th of December.

6.6 Keeping records

6.6.1 Obligation to keep records and other supporting documentation

In accordance with the provisions of the Grant Agreement under Art. 20, project partners must - for a period of five years after the payment of the balance - keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declared as eligible. They must make them available upon request (see Article 19 of the GA) or in the context of checks, reviews, audits or investigations (see Article 25 of the GA).

The beneficiaries must keep the original documents. Digital and digitalised documents are considered originals if they are authorised by the applicable national law.

6.6.2 Records and other supporting documentation on the scientific and technical implementation

Project partners must keep records and other supporting documentation on scientific and technical implementation of the action in line with the accepted standards in the respective field.

6.6.3 Right to carry out audits

The EC may — during the implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out audits on the proper implementation of the action and compliance with the obligations under the GA. Audits may be started up to two years after the payment of the balance. They will be formally notified to the PC or beneficiary concerned and will be considered to have started on the date of the formal notification.

The PC or partner concerned must provide — within the deadline requested — any information (including complete accounts, individual salary statements or other personal data) to verify compliance with the GA. The EC may request beneficiaries to provide such information to it directly.

For on-the-spot audits, the beneficiaries must allow access to their sites and premises, including to external persons or bodies, and must ensure that information requested is readily available. Information provided must be accurate, precise and complete and in the format requested, including electronic format.

6.6.4 Consequences of non-compliance

If a project partner breaches any of its obligations, costs insufficiently substantiated will be ineligible and will be rejected, and the grant may be reduced.

6.7 Open access

In accordance with the Open Access principles and the provisions of Article 17 of the GA, accessibility of the data during the project lifetime and beyond, and long-term data preservation are an essential aspect of the STAR4BBS project. The management of the data produced during the project is aimed at ensuring open access, taking also into consideration the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle, to ensure the adoption of suitable measures to preserve project results that can contain sensitive information, if any.

Thus, the project will seek a balance between openness and protection of information, commercialization and the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security etc. In case project partners need to keep specific parts of their research data closed, the choice will be explicitly justified in the Initial Data Management Plan (D8.2).

During the STAR4BBS project, mainly 4 types of data are expected to be collected and documented: experimental, observational, derived and event related.

All data shall be documented to help interested users to clearly understand and reuse them. For this reason, descriptive and substantive (i.e. how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described in line with the highest standards for research data repositories.

STAR4BBS will manage the project data with the aim to follow the FAIR principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability and to stimulate the collaboration among partners a data storage tool will be selected (e.g. Zenodo). The selection will be made having in mind the purposes and the end-users of the data stored, divided in tools appropriate for internal use and daily project activities, and tools for guaranteeing the long-term storage of STAR4BBS data. For long-term storing of data, a dedicated Zenodo Community shall be created.

FINDABILITY

Specify naming conventions to adopt; Versioning control; Metadata available to describe the datasets; All STAR4BBS documents will have a unique persistent identifier (e.g. DOI); STAR4BBS researchers will use their ORCID to associate to the STAR4BBS data; All STAR4BBS data/metadata related to daily activities stored in tools for internal purposes (accessible to the consortium); All STAR4BBS relevant

data/metadata (including publications, datasets, reports, etc) will be deposited in Zenodo and on Evidencia.eco

ACCESSIBILITY

All STAR4BBS deposited data will be openly shared, whereas possible. Measures will be put in place to protect sensitive data. If data cannot be shared or only under restriction, the conditions will be explained in Data Management Plan.

INTEROPERABILITY

All STAR4BBS datasets will specify the vocabulary used (e.g. format), aiming for the most commonly used to allow larger reuse. All STAR4BBS datasets will specify which tools are required to use the data.

REUSABILITY

All STAR4BBS datasets will be preferably licensed as CC-0 or CC-BY.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1: STAR4BBS VIRTUAL KICK-OFF MEETING MINUTES

1st September 2022

TIME	DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY	SPEAKER / WP LEADER
10:00 15'	<p>Welcome and introduction</p> <p><i>Overview of the project , PO welcome and overview</i></p>	Luana Ladu, TUB
	<p>PPT given by the coordinator, Luana Ladu on an introduction to the project - call, duration, objectives etc. Overview methodology presentation showed how objectives are tied with the different work packages tasks overall flow.</p>	
10:15 15'	<p>Icebreaker</p> <p><i>Introduction of all partners and related teams</i></p>	All
	<p>All partners introduced themselves:</p> <p>TUB (Leader of WP4 and WP8 and project coordinator)</p> <p>Luana Ladu (Project Coordinator)</p> <p>Nikola Matović</p> <p>USC (leader of WP3)</p> <p>Sara Lago</p> <p>Ana Arias</p>	

Maria Teresa Moreira (she was not present, however she will be involved in the project implementation.)

AUA (leader of WP5)

Apostolis Koutinas

Sofia Maria Ioann

Dimitris Ladakis

UNITELMA (leader of WP1)

Pergiuseppe Morone

Enrica Imbert

Giulia Borghesi

Annarita Colasante

Gülşah YILAN

NOVA (leader of WP2)

Olaf Porc

Asta Partanen

Luciano Proto Cassina

APRE (Leader WP6, WP7)

Serena Fabbrini

Giulia Treossi

Sara Silvi

ISEAL

Maira Devisscher

Jac Connell

Krisint Komives (she was not present, but she will be involved in the project)

RSB

Blanca de Ulibarri (not present, but she will be involved in the project)

	<p>UNI</p> <p>Elena Mocchio</p> <p>Adriano Ferrara</p> <p>Christina di Maria</p> <p>NEN</p> <p>(not present today)</p> <p>BAM</p> <p>Tilman Denkler</p>
<p>10:30</p> <p>30`</p>	<p>WP7 Communication, dissemination and international Cooperation</p> <p><i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities. Logo, Webpage, Internal and External communication</i></p> <p>WP8 Project Management and Financial Information</p> <p><i>Overview of tasks, Important Deadlines, Deliverables and Milestones, Monitoring of the implementation of task Joint activities with other 2 projects (e.g. advisory board)</i></p>
	<p>Luana Ladu shortly presented changes in regard to original proposal, before the WP presentations. She informed the consortium to always refer to the Grant Agreement that includes the updated proposal, and not to the originally submitted proposal (SEP). During the grant agreement negotiation, different things have been updated.</p> <p>Serena (APRE) presented WP7. She shared logo proposals for the project, specifically the template that will be used for the f2f meeting in Berlin. After the poll voting the final logo was chosen. Then the Task 7.1 was briefly explained (Strategy), including KPIs (lead by APRE but all PPs should be included). D7.1. will be done by M6. The Task 7.2 regarding Dissemination tools (visual identity, website, social media, webinars, events) was presented, with emphasis on reducing the paper and other materials for promotion and communication. Webinars will be organized by UNI. D7.2 will be completed by M34. The T7.3 will cover liaison with other projects and initiatives, with 4 deliverables connected to this task. The T7.4 will be led by</p>

UNITELMA, on exploitation and replication pathway, with related D7.8 (Roadmap, by UNITELMA, by M34). The last T7.5 is about the final conference, for the M36. It will not be possible to organize this final event with other two projects (since they started their project earlier than us). There will be a report connected to this task and conference. Luana added that there will be synergies with the other two projects financed under the same Zero Pollution cluster.

Luana continued with the WP8, introducing Task 8.1. The idea is to create mailing list of the project, and a common space on the cloud with important documents (sharing space), also for facilitating communication. Then, announcement of the financial management related ad-hoc meetings (first one already in next few months' time). All partners should pay attention to this. After the live kick-off meeting there will be on-site and online meetings (altogether 6 (3+3)). Also, important will be the WP leaders' meetings (online). Advisory board was proposed, and Joint Advisory Board with other 2 projects is an idea to be further discussed.

For the meeting in Berlin, UNITELMA will talk about the data management.

GANTT chart was shown to PPs, to keep in mind the timeline and input (interdependencies) from other WPs. Giulia (APRE) added that common mailing list is being prepared with collection of PPs contacts, for the final contact list, and we will discuss this in Berlin.

Overview of the Deliverables, Milestones, Open access features, etc on WP 8

Internal communication:

- Mailing list of the project: to be set up after the website
- Web cloud system to share documents à GDRIVE: star4bbs@gmail.com
 - o Password: \$TAR4BBS2022 (as of 14/09/2022)
 - o All useful information and docs shall be uploaded in there
 - o All ppt from the in-presence and virtual kick-off meetings shall be uploaded
 - o Upload templates for the Reporting Periods

11:00
40'

WP1 Review of SCS and labels for feedstock, bio-based materials and products

Enrica presented the WP1 objectives and outcomes. Work description included tasks (which are all starting from M1).

T1.1 is led by NOVA (review of sustainability targets; differentiate targets which are better addressed by SCS of bio feedstock and those which are better applied to bio-based products and materials);

T1.2 and T1.3 are led by UNITELMA (review and analysis of SCS and B2B labels for bio-based feedstock and for bio-based materials and products)

T1.4 is led by ISEAL (aimed at mapping all the existing SCS and labels and the impacts; by November - list with all existing labels and SCS - first draft! So, by February - integrated list of the first view of environmental and social impact)

Task 1.5 is led by TUB (review of existing monitoring systems).

Preliminary identification of the monitoring systemsà take a look at “Existing Monitoring Systems Review_draftv1”.

Timing: M1 start of all tasks; M6 D1.1; by M12 all (D1.2 (UNIT), D1.3 (ISEAL), D1.4 (TUB)).

Luana added that the policy targets priority list should be done during the next 6 months) but it should be updated during the entire project duration.

WP2 Collect of data and figures on volumes of biological feedstock and bio-based materials & products in global trade flows and selection of case studies

Olaf (NOVA) presented what will be done in WP2, including 3 tasks with 5 deliverables. Inter-project team will work also on other 2 projects. Task 2.1 is led by NOVA, starts in M1 (due dates for two deliverables are M12 and M24). Input from the whole consortium is needed. Task 2.2 also led by NOVA is from M15-M24. Input is needed by UNITELMA. Task 2.3 is led by AUA and input is needed by NOVA. In next 6 months the work to be implemented under T2.1 will be done in cooperation with with BTG & WUR, partern from the other 2 projects conducting a similar work. For the T2.3 (Selection of test cases) reciprocity is needed between NOVA and AUA.

WP3 Identification of sustainability indicators and minimum requirements

	<p>Sara presented WP3 in the name of Maria Teresa Moreira (USC). The first tasks begin in M1. The first draft of the first deliverable is due in M12. Luana suggested to have a look at the GA, because the name and timing of deliverables changed in GA in respect to the SEP. AUA will have a role as a collaborator in all the tasks. Task 3.1 will develop sustainability indicators (eg. water scarcity) to be included in the monitoring scheme. Task 3.2 will develop non-LCA indicators, different approach (eg. water circularity). Task 3.3 dwells with minimum requirements for the indicators.</p> <p>Required inputs from other PPs include WP1, WP2 and WP5.</p>	
<p>11:40 10'</p>	<p>Break</p>	
<p>11:50 40'</p>	<p>WP4 Development and demonstration of a monitoring System</p> <p>Nikola Matović presented WP4. Luana touched upon collaboration with other 2 projects - not to compete but make integration and improve synergies.</p> <p>Nikola presented how the monitoring system is envisioned à a new system to assess international and EU SCS and B2B labels against sustainability indicators. Sustainability content and outcome indicators will cover: environmental, social and economic aspects.</p> <p>Several phases of the monitoring system: wp leader and project partners will test internally the system, then together with WP leaders of other WPs – schemes, labels and value chains shall already be selected - we will do the feasibility testing to verify the soundness and applicability of the monitoring system. If all goes well - get the feedback of the selected stakeholders - see if they have final remarks to be taken into account (AB and external stakeholders)</p> <p>Main goals:</p> <p>1 concept of the monitoring system (developed and tested)</p> <p>Assessment of at least 60 SCS and labels with the new monitoring system+ Ranking of SCS and B2B labels</p>	

T4.1 – Conceptualization of the monitoring system

The goal is to be able to design a monitoring system to be tested in Jan 2024. Alignment process to put everything together in December (analysis of the policy environment, schemes, indicators side) and based on that have meetings to discuss the strategy to be followed in terms of engaging stakeholders (identify who we want to involve in the validation and refinement workshop)

Methodology:

The MS shall include 3 levels:

- System level (e.g. monitor scope of application, owner, geographical coverage of the schemes and labels)
- Content level: sustainability indicators and traceability
- Outcomes: effectiveness and impact (depending on data availability) of existing certification schemes and labels.

T4.2 - Development of a monitoring system:

The development of the monitoring system and user interface, will involve pulling input from other WPs into a format that can be used for testing (T6.3)

The testing will be used to further iterate the monitoring system, feeding in the final version of the tool

To facilitate use of the tool: provide transparency into the methodology and deliver a clear understanding of the results emerging from the analysis.

T4.3 - Testing and applying newly developed monitoring system:

Testing performed in the previous task will be used together with the outcomes of the review of schemes and labels and be brought into the tool

SCS and labels owners will be provided with the opportunity to identify any problems with this source data and labels

The schemes and labels will then be assessed using the monitoring system, which will be adjusted accordingly

Once all the adjustments to the monitoring system tool have been made (T4.2) the process will be repeated for all feedstock schemes and labels reviewed in WP1

Required inputs from the first 3 work packages

WP5 Assessment of costs of the adoption of SCS & labels and feasibility of B2B labels

Apostolis presented WP5. There are 6 tasks, from process design to externalization of costs and benefits and evaluation of feasibility potential. Task 5.1 starts from M6, led by AUA and USC as involved partner. T5.2 will be led by USC with support of AUA.

T5.3 - led by USC, supported by AUA.

T5.4 will be led by AUA with the help of USC. T5.5 is led by AUA and with support of NOVA, UNIT, USC. T5.6 will be led by UNIT and will involve PPs: AUA, USC, ISEAL, TUB, RBS.

There is 1 milestone (by M24) and 3 deliverables.

Luana added that the value chain selection is really important, especially in the upcoming months.

WP6 Stakeholder involvement, and development of Recommendations

Serena (APRE) presented the WP6. It starts from the beginning of the project until its end. The objectives concern stakeholder's engagement. It is tied with co-creation workshop and other events. There are 3 tasks. T6.1 is led by APRE but supported by ISEAL, TUB, NOVA, UNIT. Brand new matrix will be developed. Stakeholder map by M5. T6.2 is about the co-creation workshops, at least 5 online (led by APRE). T6.3 is led by NOVA with support by TUB, ISEAL, UNIT, APRE. D6.3 will be realised by NOVA (by M36).

To set up a standard template to gather partners' suggestions for the different categories of stakeholders

Data issue: GDPR issue, meet with existing regulations concerning the share of direct contacts (e.g the ones the organizations in the consortium already have).

12:30	Next Steps, open discussion
	<p>Luana started by saying how important is to be well prepared for the live meeting in Berlin (thoughts on tasks' implementation). She noted that she will collect all the ppts from today to share them in one joint folder on the cloud. We can then decide which virtual place to use for this purpose in the future.</p> <p>Regarding the mailing list, all PPs should tell APRE who should receive all emails about the project.</p> <p>By Friday we will send the link for the attendance list of the Kick-off in Berlin (also for the meals). It will be a hybrid event (recorded live).</p> <p>On 5th October there is a workshop in Brussels which can be attended (Projects2projects). Luana added that each PP can share such event links etc. connected with our project, with all other partners.</p> <p>Luana also put emphasis on the deliverables that are due in next 6 months.</p> <p>Webpage for the project? Later, each organization can put the link on their pages that leads to the STAR4BBS project's webpage.</p> <p>The template for project presentations will be shared with PPs in 6-7 days' time.</p>
12:55	Closing by project coordinator
End of the Meeting	

7.2 Annex 2 - STAR4BBS KOICK-OFF MEETING MINUTES

14th- 15th September 2022

Room FH 302

Fraunhoferstraße 33-36

D-10587

Berlin

AGENDA WITH MINUTES

14-15/09/2022

Hybrid event

Zoom link:

<https://tu-berlin.zoom.us/j/66126806392?pwd=a0xUYjVDc2hqbdUwQUwwL0JOZCtPdZ09>

Participants day 1 (14th of September)

1. Luana Ladu, TUB
2. Nikola Matovic, TUB
3. Prof. Knut Blind, TUB
4. Enrica Imbert, UNITELMA
5. Prof. Piergiuseppe Morone, UNITELMA
6. Prof. Apostolis Koutinas, AUA
7. Dimitris Ladakis, AUA
8. Prof. Maria Teresa Moreira, USC
9. Gumersindo Feijoo, USC
10. Maira Devisscher, ISEAL
11. Olaf Porc, NOVA
12. Luciano Proto Cassina, NOVA
13. Chiara Pocaterra - APRE
14. Serena Fabbrini, APRE
15. Giulia Treossi, APRE
16. Tilman Denkler, BAM
17. Blanca de Ulibarri, RSB

Online participants:

1. Stefania Rocca, REA
2. Sara Lago, USC
3. Annalisa Paccapelo, UNITELMA
4. Kristin Komives, ISEAL
5. Zeynep Beyhan, UNITELMA
6. Naomi Black, ISEAL

Day 1 – 14th September 2022 | 13:00-18:30

TIME	DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY	SPEAKER / WP LEADER
12:00	Lunch	
13:00	Registration and coffee welcome	
13.15 30'	Welcome and introduction <i>Overview of the project, PO welcome and overview</i>	Luana Ladu, TUB Knut Blind, TUB Stefania Rocca, REA
<p>The kick-off meeting started with the welcoming message of Professor Knut Blind. He gave an introduction emphasising the importance of the Quality Infrastructure (in particular the standards and conformity assessment) in achieving the SDGs. He highlighted that the EU is recognizing the importance of standards for sustainability and that it is very important to implement projects such the STAR4BBS project, in this topic. He also added that he is the Chair of CEN-CENELEC Working Group STAIR (Standards, Innovation & Research) in Brussels and can aid us with dissemination of events and project results so we can contact him for this purpose.</p>		

The STAR4BBS project coordinator, Luana Ladu gave an overview and brief introduction to the two days of the meeting, sharing the agenda and providing a brief introduction to the project (Project summary, main objectives and overview of Work Packages).

The Project officer of the European Research Executive Agency (REA), Stefania Rocca, gave a general presentation on the topic of reporting and project management (as well as dissemination and exploitation), providing the context to our project. As already mentioned on the 16th June, 2022 (Clustering event), she highlighted that the implementation of STAR4BBS should be aligned with the other two projects: HARMONITOR, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, including mutual synergies with policy alignment and engagement with stakeholders.

She continued with reminding the Project Partners (PPs) about important articles of the GA regarding beneficiaries and coordinator relationship and sharing information. She then briefly talked about the Amendment to the GA. Mentioned was the Reporting Timeline – 2 reporting periods with the deadline for submission (60 days). She briefly reminded of engagement in activities – communication and dissemination, with a list of tools for giving support to partners (eg. free of charge service for booster with open call twice a year).

In the end she reminded us of the upcoming event – EU Bioeconomy Conference 2022 (hybrid; registration link [here](#)) on 6-7th October. She also invited us to upload our profiles on the database with the provided link (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/work-as-an-expert>) in the presentation.

<p>13:45 30'</p>	<p>Icebreaker</p> <p>During this session, participants symbolically “kicked-off” the meeting by kicking a ball and passing it to each other, also saying their names and the institutions they come from. Each ball receiver had to repeat the name of the previous participant. In the second part of the session, participants did an icebreaker activity called “Two truths, one lie”. Each of them had to write 3 sentences describing them of which one was not truthful. The other participants had to guess what the lie was. In this way, they got to meet each other better and strengthen the bonds, for future cooperation.</p>	
<p>14:15 30'</p>	<p>WP8 Project Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	<p>Luana Ladu, Juliane Rosengart, TUB</p>

Luana provided a presentation on project management. In particular, the following bodies of the project were proposed:

Project Manager: Luana Ladu from TU Berlin

CoDNOC: Serena Fabbrini from APRE

Project Management Committee (PMC):

one member for each organization

Members:

TUB: Luana Ladu

UNITELMA: Enrica Imbert

APRE: Serena Fabbrini

NOVA: Olaf Porc

USC: Sara Lago

UNI:

AUA: Apostolis Koutinas

NEN:

BAM: Tilman Denkler

RSB: Blanca de Ulibarri
 ISEAL: Maira Devisscher

In the proposal the following members of the Advisory Board were proposed: SPRING, TextileExchange, UNFSS, Institute of the Environment of the University of Minnesota. In addition, UNIDO was conducted after project approval.

Luana presented the idea of having a joint Advisory Board with the other 2 projects. In this regard, Piergiuseppe noted that 3 projects might be too much for them to monitor, so we have to choose carefully. Chiara added that we have to be very specific in what we need from them. Luana replied that it is still up for discussion, and that we can establish a strategy. Some PPs added that as the other 2 projects have already started, maybe they moved forward on this.

Internal communication: each WP and task leader should organize online meetings internal to their WP and tasks. There will also be different project meetings of the entire consortium. T8.1. for Intra WP communication - it is advisable to have monthly meetings, for eg. within WPs etc.

Intra-periodic reports: Stefania suggested partners to also prepare these short types of reports, like 2-3 pages max, every 2-3 months for example. TUB will lead this process. They can be uploaded in PDF in the system (there will be a form made for this). These reports can be handy to check the outcomes' progress, to find solutions if needed etc.

Partners discussed the location of future on-site meetings. One suggestion was to have it during the International forum on Bioeconomy in Florence. They tentatively agreed to have the M12 meeting in Athens and the M24 in Rome. Yet to decide where to have the M36 meeting (potential locations mentioned were Brussels and Berlin).

One important emphasis from Luana: all published papers must be in open access journals. Luana also highlighted the need to refer to the Grant Agreement document and not to the submitted proposal (SEP), considering that different updates were included in the Grant Agreement.

14:45 60'	WPI Review of SCS and labels for feedstock, bio-based materials and products <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Task 1.1 (NOVA) ○ <i>Task 1.2 & Task 1.3 (UNITELMA)</i> ○ Task 1.4 (ISEAL) ○ Task 1.5 (TUB) ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	Enrica Imbert, Piergiuseppe Morone UNITELMA
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Enrica Imbert provided a presentation on WPI, including objectives, methodology, timelines and an overview of the different tasks.

Olaf (NOVA) posed a question for PPs and opened discussion on which SDGs we should focus on. USC partners indicated that indicators and targets should be closely linked. Luana highlighted that Task 1.1 should revise existing policies, regulations and strategies with the objective of identifying "policy priorities" to be addressed within the STAR4BBS. SCS and labels should contribute to achieving these targets. Maira (ISEAL) was concerned with the timeline and process for identification and selection of indicators, and she proposed effective coordination with other WPs.

Kristin (ISEAL) through the Zoom noted that we should always be aware of the target groups: who this Regulation is targeted at? For e.g. for local governments most labels do not apply to. We have to focus on systems relevant to B2B context.

Luana proposed an internal meeting for discussing these issues and arranging another meeting with other 2 project coordinators, as well as with Silvia Maltagliati.

Piergiuseppe: When we look at indicators and standards, we have to be aware of macro-assessment of indicators - we have to establish a link to our micro-way of doing it and choosing the indicators.

It was agreed that each Task leader will prepare a short description of the strategy for: 1) identify the sources of documents/elements to be consulted; 2) how to assess them. For example, NOVA will share in 2 weeks' time a strategy on how to select policies to be analyzed and also a strategy on how to assess them. The same will be done for all the tasks of WP1.

15:45 15'	Break	
16:00 45'	WP2 Collection of data and figures on volumes of biological feedstock and bio-based materials & products in global trade flows and selection of case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Task 2.1 (NOVA) ○ Task 2.2 (NOVA) ○ Task 2.3 (AUA) ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	Olaf Porc, NOVA
<p>Olaf Porc presented WP2. PPs briefly discussed about the need to share all the links related to project themes among the Consortium, for eg. which databases to use (eg. Ecolabel Index). This will facilitate the identification of synergies among tasks and WPs. For example, the Matrix to be developed in WP1 for assessing the SCS and labels, should be developed keeping in mind the work to be conducted in Wp2 and WP4. It was also suggested to have a look at the matrixes developed under the implementation of STAR-ProBio and to build upon them</p> <p>One reference was mentioned - Rosenboom et al. (2022). Bioplastics for a circular economy (critical issues outlined).</p>		
16:45 45'	WP3 Identification of sustainability indicators and minimum requirements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Task 3.1 (USC) ○ Task 3.2 (USC) ○ Task 3.3 (USC) ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	Maria Teresa Moreira, USC
<p>Maria Teresa Moreira provided an overview of the different tasks of WP3.</p>		
17:30 45'	WP7 Communication, dissemination and international Cooperation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Task 7.1 (APRE) ○ Task 7.2 (APRE) ○ Task 7.3 (TUB) 	Serena Fabbrini, APRE

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	
<p>Serena Fabbrini from APRE, provided an overview of WP7.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of the Deliverables, Milestones, Open access features, etc on WP 8 <p>Internal communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mailing list of the project: to be set up after the website - Web cloud system to share documents à GDRIVE: star4bbs@gmail.com <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Password: \$TAR4BBS2022 (as of 14/09/2022) o All useful information and docs shall be uploaded in there o All ppt from the in-presence and virtual kick-off meetings shall be uploaded <p>Upload templates for the Reporting Periods</p> <p>TUB raised an issue of the “heaviness” of the project’s PPT template and the need to reduce the original file size, while maintaining its quality. Also, the cover page title box is not functioning properly for some of the project partners, so it needs to be taken look at.</p>		
18:15	Photoshoot and overview of the 2nd day	
19:30: SOCIAL DINNER CAFE AM NEUEN SEE, LICHTENSTEINALLEE 2 · 10787 BERLIN		

Day 2 – 15th September 2022 | 9:00-13:15

1. Luana Ladu, TUB
2. Nikola Matovic, TUB
3. Rosengart Juliane, TUB
4. Carolin Schmidt, TUB
5. Enrica Imbert, UNITELMA
6. Prof. Piergiuseppe Morone, UNITELMA
7. Prof. Apostolis Koutinas, AUA
8. Dimitris Ladakis, AUA
9. Prof. Maria Teresa Moreira, USC
10. Gumersindo Feijoo, USC
11. Maira Devisscher, ISEAL
12. Olaf Porc, NOVA
13. Luciano Proto Cassina, NOVA
14. Serena Fabbrini, APRE
15. Giulia Treossi, APRE
16. Tilman Denkler, BAM
17. Blanca de Ulibarri, RSB

Online participants

1. Stefania Rocca, REA
2. Sara Lago, USC
3. Annalisa Paccapelo, UNITELMA
4. Marco Cardinaletti, UNITELMA
5. Federica Fugaroli, UNI

09.00 15'	Welcome coffee	
9:15 15'	Recap by the project coordinator	Luana Ladu, TUB
<p>Day 2 started with Luana providing an overview of the methodology and of the objectives of each work package.. She touched briefly on the review of WPS, starting with WP1 as it is the most important to align its objectives among PPs as it is the WP which already starts in the first 6 months of the project.</p>		
9:30 45'	WP4 Development and demonstration of a monitoring system <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Task 4.1 (ISEAL) ● Task 4.2 (TUB) ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	Luana Ladu, TUB
<p>Nikola provided a presentation of WP4, on how the monitoring system is envisioned as a new system to assess international and EU SCS and B2B labels against sustainability indicators. Sustainability content and outcome indicators will cover: environmental, social and economic aspects.</p> <p>Several phases of the monitoring system: WP leader and project partners will test internally the system, then together with WP leaders of other WPs – schemes, labels and value chains shall already be selected - we will do the feasibility testing to verify the soundness and applicability of the monitoring system. If all goes well, we will then get the</p>		

feedback of the selected stakeholders, then see if they have final remarks to be taken into account (APs and external stakeholders).

T4.1 – Conceptualization of the monitoring system

The goal is to be able to design a monitoring system to be tested in Jan 2024. Alignment process to put everything together in December (analysis of the policy environment, schemes, indicators side) and based on that have meetings to discuss the strategy to be followed in terms of engaging stakeholders (identify who we want to involve in the validation and refinement workshop).

T4.2 - Development of a monitoring system

The development of the monitoring system and user interface, will involve pulling input from other WPs into a format that can be used for testing (T6.3)

The testing will be used to further iterate the monitoring system, feeding in the final version of the tool.

To facilitate use of the tool: provide transparency into the methodology and deliver a clear understanding of the results emerging from the analysis.

T4.3 - Testing and applying newly developed monitoring system

Testing performed in the previous task will be used together with the outcomes of the review of schemes and labels and be brought into the tool. SCS and labels owners will be provided with the opportunity to identify any problems with this source data and labels.

The schemes and labels will then be assessed using the monitoring system, which will be adjusted accordingly.

Once all the adjustments to the monitoring system tool have been made (T4.2) the process will be repeated for all feedstock schemes and labels reviewed in WP1. Required inputs from the first 3 work packages.

The concept of the monitoring system will be built partly on the results of Task 1.5. In addition, stakeholder inputs will be collected. In particular, ISEAL is proposing to organize a validation meeting with stakeholders in December, to present a first concept of the monitoring system. However, before that, bilateral discussion with different stakeholders will take place. For this purpose, different stakeholder types will be identified and selected. CO-creation workshop should be more as a validation.

During the meeting, there was a discussion on the potential users of the monitoring framework. In particular, policy makers, industrial actors.

Methodology for the monitoring system: will be established after consultation. Bringing all the elements together.

<p>10:15 45'</p>	<p>WP5 Assessment of costs of the adoption of SCS & labels and feasibility of B2B labels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Task 5.1 (AUA)</i> ○ <i>Task 5.2 & Task 5.3 (USC)</i> 	<p>Apostolis Koutinas, AUA</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o <i>Task 5.4 (AUA)</i> o <i>Task 5.5 (AUA)</i> ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	
<p>Apostolis provided an overview of WP5. Some tasks were presented by Maite (USC): Apostolis suggested comparing costs and benefits between certified and non-certified products. Discussion with Luana on Dropping vs functional product, regarding benchmarking (certification of feedstock compared to non-certified products, e.g. comparing PLA certified plastics with non-certified).</p>		
11:00 15'	Break	
11:15 45'	WP6 Stakeholder involvement, and development of Recommendations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Objectives, duration, partners involved, activities and deliverables, milestones and risks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o <i>Task 6.1 (APRE)</i> o <i>Task 6.2 (APRE)</i> ▪ <i>Open discussion</i> 	Serena Fabbrini, APRE
<p>UNI (Frederica Fugaroli) briefly presented the role of UNI in the project, especially ties to the WP6.</p> <p>Serena (APRE) presented the overview of the WP6. System needs to be developed for the stakeholder map - APRE will send an email in the next weeks to collect contacts from all PPs' partners and collaborators. Also, a framework will be developed (to set up a standard template to gather partners' suggestions for the different categories of stakeholders) and a shared document will be kept open for further collection of stakeholders' contacts.</p> <p>Discussion about the data management - contact details of the stakeholders (private contacts should not be shared). We must be aligned with GDPR rules at all times.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data issue: GDPR issue, meet with existing regulations concerning the share of direct contacts (e.g the ones the organizations in the consortium already have). 		
12:00 40'	WP8 Project Management and Financial Information (part II) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Financial Information</i> ▪ <i>Data Management Plan</i> 	Juliane Rosengart, TUB Marco Cardinaletti, UNITELMA
<p>Juliane Rosengart presented financial support, together with Carolin Schmidt. Short overview of the financial rules. A webinar on financial topics will be organized within the next 4 weeks for financial officers also to be included and present along with their project managers. For any questions, Juliane is available.</p> <p>Marco (UNITELMA) presented a data management plan concept, with brief discussion with PPs about data storing.</p> <p>Each partner present at the meeting these two days agreed and gave permission for publishing photos with them, on the project's social networks and for project related purposes.</p>		
12:40	Open Discussion	
<p>Luana opened the discussion by stressing out the importance of having regular or periodic online meetings. In M6 there will be our first online meeting, but before that, for example</p>		

in mid-December the first Zoom call can be organized for all PPs. Before that WP1 PPs can prepare their first draft of the agreed structure for data collection.

At the end of October WP1 leaders will have an internal meeting for the involved PPs. Next week there will be a short meeting organized between those partners to look at the timeline (maybe Thursday 22nd October at 11h? Enrica (WP1 lead) will send a Zoom invitation).

We also discussed the next steps. Deliverables that are due in the next 6 months, and the event Projects2projects in Brussels (Luana asked for some project's materials to bring to the event).

Serena stated that they will provide guidelines for the newsletter, share stories about the project etc.

Luana said that there will be the Bioeconomy summit in Berlin (organized every 2 years) and that we can get a spot for the project, chair some sessions, present some results there (maybe also with other 2 projects). Serena said that this would be part of dissemination activities. Luana reminded us that we should also publish papers and make policy briefs. Some PPs reminded that Evidensia will also serve for disseminating the results. Project website link will be shared soon, when it is up and running, as well as the Cordis link.

13:10	Closing by project coordinator
13:20	Lunch

7.3 Annex 3 - Creation of Inter-Project teams under the call HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZERO POLLUTION-07

BLOCKS	HARMONITOR	STAR4BBS	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
Coordination and Management	Sergio Ugarte (SQ), s.ugarte@sqconsult.com	Luana Ladu (TUB), luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de	Iris Vural Gursel (WR), iris.vuralgursel@wur.nl
Review of labels and SCS	Ciara McCarthy (PbN), cmccarthy@preferredbynature.org M5-M31 For the alignment of methodology Stefan Majer (DBFZ), Stefan.Majer@dbfz.de M1-M35	Enrica Imbert (Unitelma), enrica.imbert@unitelma.sapienza.it (M1-M12) (For the impact assessment) Maira Devisscher (ISEAL) maira@isealalliance.org (M1-M12)	Iris Vural Gursel (WR-WFBR), iris.vuralgursel@wur.nl María Pérez Alonso (CIRCE) mperez@fcirce.es M3-M11
Global Trade Flows	Martijn Vis (BTG), vis@btgworld.com M1- M33	Olaf Porc (Nova Institute) olaf.porc@nova-institut.de M1- M24	Myrna van Leeuwen (WR-WEcR), myrna.vanleeuwen@wur.nl M6-M14
Concept of the monitoring system	Martin Junginger (UU), H.M.Junginger@uu.nl M10-M36 For the alignment of methodology Stefan Majer (DBFZ), Stefan.Majer@dbfz.de M1-M35	Kristin Komiev (ISEAL) kristin@isealalliance.org M2- M12 Luana Ladu (TUB), luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de Nikola Matovik(TUB) matovik@tu-berlin.de	Mathilde Crêpy (ECOS), mathilde.crepy@ecostandard.org Samy Porteron (ECOS) samy.porteron@ecostandard.org M1-M15
Implementation and testing of the monitoring system	Martin Junginger (UU), H.M.Junginger@uu.nl M18-M36 For the establishment of the validating platform Stefan Majer (DBFZ),	Luana Ladu (TUB), luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de M2-M36 For indicators: Maria Teresa Moreira (USC) maite.moreira@usc.es M1-M34	Iris Vural Gursel (WR-WFBR), (testing on scheme/labels) M12-22 iris.vuralgursel@wur.nl Loek Verwijst (CU), (pilot audit check) M12-29 lverwijst@controlunion.com

	Stefan.Majer@dbfz.de M12-M36		Samy Portheron (ECOS), (implement feedback) M22-30 samy.porteron@ecostandard.org
Analysis of costs and benefits	Birka Wicke (RU), birka.wicke@ru.nl M7-M35	Apostolis Koutinas (AUA), akoutinas@aua.gr M6-M36	Lusine Aramyan (WR-WEcR) lusine.aramyan@wur.nl Luuk Vissers (WR-WEcR) luuk.vissers@wur.nl M4-34
Bio-based value chain selection for CBA & feasibility	Birka Wicke (RU), birka.wicke@ru.nl M7-M21	Case studies: Olaf Porc (Nova Institute) olaf.porc@nova-institut.de Apostolis Koutinas (AUA), akoutinas@aua.gr M3-M18 Feasibility Enrica Imbert (Unitelma), enrica.imbert@unitelma.sapienza.it M24-M36	María Pérez Alonso (CIRCE) – preliminary list mperez@fcirce.es Lusine Aramyan (WR-WEcR) lusine.aramyan@wur.nl Loek Verwijst (CU) verwijst@controlunion.com M4-11
Communication & dissemination of the results	Sergio Ugarte (SQ), s.ugarte@sqconsult.com	Serena Fabbrini (APRE) fabbrini@apre.it M1-M36	Annie Kalimeri (White) akalimeri@white-research.eu

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